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Programme of the European Learning Circle for Sustainable Bicycle Logistics

Deliverable 5.3

Version 1.0

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List of abbreviations

B2B	Business to business
B2C	Business to consumer
CEO	Chief executive officer
CET	Central European time
D	Deliverable
DUT	Driving Urban Transitions
ELC	European Learning Circle
Q&A	Questions and answers
R&D	Research and development
V	Version

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Administrative information

Basic information on the SuCoLo project and this deliverable:

Project title	SuCoLo: Fostering sustainable consumer behaviour with inclusive bicycle logistics infrastructure in urban outskirts
Project coordinator	Salzburg Research Forschungsgesellschaft mbH (SRFG), Salzburg, Austria; project coordinator: Michael Thelen
Project partners	Independent L. ONLUS (IND), Italy Sustainability InnoCenter (SIC), Sweden VIABIRDS Technologies GmbH (VIA), Austria Universität Leipzig (ULEI), Germany Südtiroler Transportstrukturen AG – Green Mobility Department (STA), Italy
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Purpose of the document

The current document outlines the structure and outcomes of the European Learning Circle for Sustainable Bicycle Logistics of the SuCoLo project. As a main communication outlet of SuCoLo, the European Learning Circle served to bring together city and regional officials, logistics and courier companies, e-commerce professionals, researchers, urban living lab coordinators, and anyone passionate about sustainable urban mobility and logistics to discuss the potential adoption and scaling of SuCoLo's outputs and products in their specific case. Divided into a three-part series, the European Learning Circles discussed three thematic topics: (1) integrating cargo bikes into the city's shared mobility system and local shop deliveries, (2) testing a mobile micro-hub with cargo bikes piloted by a local courier service, and (3) developing and analyzing digital nudges on e-commerce sites to promote cargo bike consumer delivery choices. More broadly, the European Learning Circle was a tool to gain external feedback regarding SuCoLo's three research pilots and to harness these insights in SuCoLo's last project phase, *"Prepare and organize take-up measures in follower cities"* to maximise the exploitation of SuCoLo results beyond the project's duration. The planning of the European Learning Circle was developed by Sustainability InnoCenter and Salzburg Research, with the cooperation of all consortium partners.

Executive Summary

This deliverable provides a report on the activities carried out under Task 5.2, “Support adoption and scaling in follower cities.” The main focus of this task was the organisation of a European Learning Circle (ELC) on Sustainable Bicycle Logistics, bringing together representatives from interested cities, logistics providers, and other relevant stakeholders.

The ELC aimed to facilitate a two-way exchange of knowledge and experiences among experts, focusing on the outcomes of three SuCoLo research pilots implemented in Salzburg, Merano, and Leipzig, each addressing different approaches to sustainable logistics and mobility.

Three online exchange sessions were held on 18 September, 25 September, and 2 October 2025. The sessions were organised by Sustainability InnoCenter and supported by all project partners. In total, 97 participants attended the ELC.

At the beginning of each session, the SuCoLo team presented the key findings of the respective pilot, followed by a Q&A session with participants. The second part of each session consisted of small-group discussions (approximately five participants per group), focusing on reflections on the pilot and its potential for adaptation and scaling.

The outcomes and summaries of these discussions were subsequently used as input for the preparation of the next activity under Task 4.3, “Adaptation plans of follower cities,” including the organisation of the workshops.

1. Introduction and task description

This deliverable is based on the activities and insights from the international European Learning Circle (ELC) for Sustainable Bicycle Logistics. It sought to facilitate a two-way exchange among experts on the outcomes of the three SuCoLo research pilots in Salzburg, Merano and Leipzig, all of which focused on different sustainable logistics and mobility modalities. This document describes the three virtual exchange sessions that took place on 18 September, 25 September and 2 October 2025, along with its outcome and implications.

The work was realized within WP5 “Dissemination & take up measures” with a focus on T5.2 “Support adoption and scaling in follower cities.” With a targeted outreach strategy, the Learning Circles involved city and regional officials, logistics and courier companies, e-commerce professionals, researchers, urban living lab coordinators, and anyone passionate about sustainable urban mobility and logistics. Based on findings from the Learning Circles, the research pilots can be fine-tuned. Additionally, the ELC inputs were considered in planning and preparing for the workshops for the following cities, organised within Task 4.3. Adaptation plans of follower cities. Moreover, the last outputs in the project’s final phase *“Prepare and organize take-up measures in follower cities” can be informed from this feedback (e.g., D5.4 Recommendations for Sustainable Urban Bicycle Logistics Policies)*.

The lead partner for this task was Sustainability InnoCenter, with the support of all partners and the advisory board.

1.1. Target groups, outreach and sampling

The target groups we aimed to reach at the preparation for the European Learning Circle were city and regional officials, logistics and courier companies, e-commerce professionals, researchers, urban living lab coordinators, as well as anyone passionate about sustainable urban mobility and logistics, in order to discuss the potential adoption and scaling of SuCoLo’s outputs and products in their specific contexts.

Registration for the workshops was open to all, with participation confirmed by the SuCoLo team. The registration period ran from 25 July to 1 October, during which a total of 210 registrations were received across the three sessions. In total, 97 participants attended the ELC, with a maximum of 42 participants in a single session. In addition, the organisers contacted registered participants who did not attend the events and shared information about the pilots with them.

A core method of recruiting participants for the ELC was through personal outreach. To support this, dedicated invitation materials were developed. In total, more than 400 personalised invitations were sent to various stakeholders within the networks of the project partners.

In parallel, a communication campaign was led by Sustainability InnoCenter. This included the creation of banners and texts that were published on the SuCoLo website. A series of posts was also published on the SuCoLo LinkedIn page to build awareness of the sessions. Moreover, an event page was created on LinkedIn. Project partners actively shared this content and supplemented it with outreach through their own channels, including social media platforms (LinkedIn, Facebook, Instagram), newsletters, and websites.

Figure 1 User communities of SuCoLo results

Figure 2 Screenshot of the news post on the SuCoLo website

Figure 3 Examples of banners used in the communication campaign to reach the target groups

Figure 4 Screenshot of the ELC event page on LinkedIn

2. Session 1

2.1. Overview

The first session of the ELC took place on 18 September 2025 from 11:00 to 12:00 CET on Zoom. The seminar explored the integration of cargo bikes into the city's shared mobility system and the fostering of cargo bike delivery services for local shops, based on the results of the Merano pilot, Italy.

Figure 5 Social media banner promoting the first ELC session

The speakers of the event were **Valentina Mena**, Project Manager for Bicycle Mobility, Green Mobility, STA - Südtiroler Transportstrukturen AG, and **Günther Ennemoser**, Project Manager, Cooperativa sociale independent L., who presented the SuCoLo pilot in Merano.

Merano pilot project – Move to Cargo

Key - facts

- **What is working**
 - Citizens gradually built confidence in the service also through **marketing and promo campaign: extremely important**
 - Active involvement of **shopkeepers as project multiplier**. Through feedbacks-rounds.
 - Clear **communication and documentation, designed for all**.
- **What is not working**
 - Pick-up box locations not suitable.
 - **App/tech overload**: citizens are reluctance to register on new platforms (*managing order platform*)
 - Adoption of the Eco-Mover e-scooter for people with disabilities. Concerns and psychosocial barriers, including perceived stigma among older non-disabled users.
- **Lesson learnt and next steps**
 - **Location of pick-up station** – must be based on **scientific datas** (adjustment of pick-up box location based on Logistic Living Labs of Leipzig simulation).
 - Future of services: **under discussion** with city and stakeholders.
 - New mobility services is something **innovative and uncommon for Merano**, which **requires time** for users to adapt—especially when not explicitly requested by the population, even if the **benefits are recognized**.

Inclusiveness & Accessibility for all

THE APPLIED SPECIFIC INTERVENTION STRATEGIES IN MERANO:

1. **GENERAL ACCESSIBILITY FOR ALL**
 - 1.1 Mapping of POIs in the pilot area regarding accessibility for all
 - 1.2 VR-Tour describing the accessibility of the pilot site (pick-up station)
2. **ACCESSIBILITY AND USABILITY OF THE PILOT PROJECT**
 - 2.1 Elaboration of PEBA - Plan for the Elimination of Architectural Barriers for the pick-up station at MIND
 - 2.2 Rental of an accessible “cargo bike” in the form of an electric scooter (EcoMover for all)
3. **ACCESSIBLE COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION**
 - 3.1 Translation of the SuCoLo project description and pilot measures into certified easy language
 - 3.2 Translation of the SuCoLo project description and pilot measures into International Sign language

Figure 6 Key facts about the Merano project and its focus on inclusiveness and accessibility

The event organised by SIC (Sweden), with support from project partners from Austria, Germany and Italy.

The session was opened with a welcome from the moderator, followed by a welcome speech and a brief introduction to the project by **Michael Thelen**, Innovation Researcher at Salzburg Research and SuCoLo Project Coordinator. This was followed by the pilot presentation delivered by Valentina Mena and Günther Ennemoser. After the presentations, there was a Q&A session with the speakers, giving participants the opportunity to ask questions and engage in discussion.

Participants then took part in work in breakout rooms to collaborate and share insights. The event concluded with closing remarks to wrap up the session.

Figure 7 Agenda of the first ELC session

The event was moderated by **Chisem Karagyozy** (SIC), while representatives of the project partners facilitated the activities in the breakout rooms. Both the moderator and the facilitators received instructions and guidelines specifically prepared for the first ELC session. In addition, preparatory meetings were organised prior to the series of the ELC sessions.

In the first session, five groups were formed among interested participants, with discussions held in two rounds, each consisting of 4-6 participants per group.

The discussions were supported using Miro, an online interactive whiteboard platform, where responses were recorded and organised for analysis.

Figure 8 First ELC session, 18 September 2025 (Zoom)

2.2. Synthesis and outcome

In the first round of discussion, participants shared their views on the Merano pilot, highlighting the aspects they found interesting or noteworthy, as well as identifying both its strengths and areas for improvement.

Participants noted that the pilot has significant potential to contribute to sustainability goals beyond local shopping, provided it is more closely integrated with city initiatives and stakeholder engagement is strengthened. They reflected on Merano's broader sustainability context, observing that, although the city has strong sustainable tourism credentials, challenges such as over-tourism and sustainability awareness remain.

The pilot was also seen as scalable, with potential applications including **waste collection**, and participants emphasised the importance of initiatives that encourage behavioural change towards more sustainable mobility.

Accessibility was identified as a key factor for success. The pilot is on the right track for inclusion, but further measures are needed to make it truly accessible for all target groups. While the service is designed to be inclusive, issues remain – elderly users are hesitant to use electric scooters or larger vehicles. Barrier-free access should extend to tourists as well, but app registration requires an Italian ID, creating a limitation. Suggestions included placing pick-up stations near residential areas to improve convenience.

Several participants highlighted the importance of strengthening the pilot's **visibility and communication**. They stressed that clearer and more active promotional efforts are essential for increasing engagement and demonstrating the value of the pilot to the community. It was noted that many residents, especially families and older adults, may not yet be aware of the service. Participants also pointed out that, although the pilot is part of a broader sustainability pact, this link is not communicated clearly. Using early adopters as ambassadors was suggested as an effective way to encourage wider uptake.

Participants appreciated the **digital application** as a useful tool for managing the service. However, they also noted that further improvements in digital integration and usability are necessary to support smooth adoption, especially among less tech-savvy users. The presence of multiple mobility apps was identified as a challenge, as it may create confusion, particularly for older residents. In addition, the lack of translation support, including the current limitations of AI-based translation tools, reduces accessibility for non-Italian speakers and may hinder broader engagement.

Participants noted that strengthening **operational guidelines**, providing training opportunities, and improving coordination with stakeholders would significantly enhance the pilot's functionality and reliability. They discussed several practical considerations, including the need for clear instructions on the assembly, maintenance, and repair of cargo bikes, and suggested that public training may be necessary to support broader use. They also pointed out that the pricing scheme and target groups require further clarification. Cooperation with **local shops** was highlighted as essential to ensure that the service is both convenient and effective.

In the second round of discussion, participants discussed how the pilot could be adapted and implemented in other cities or regions. They noted that **careful consideration of local**

infrastructure, early engagement of key stakeholders, sustainable funding mechanisms, and inclusive design for all user groups are critical to ensure the pilot moves beyond a trial phase and becomes a sustainable service.

Successful adaptation depends on proper **infrastructure**, including well-designed cycle paths, electrification, charging and lighting facilities, and last-mile delivery routes to reduce congestion and illegal parking. In larger cities or areas with high traffic, adaptations such as traffic restrictions or high-powered cargo bikes in mountainous regions may be required. Smaller cities, such as Salzburg, Merano, and Bolzano, were identified as particularly suitable, while dense urban centres may present challenges, especially regarding accessibility for disabled users.

Seasonal factors, such as limited daylight hours in winter, may also affect usage.

Securing public investments and leveraging cooperation with funded projects were considered critical. **Financial incentives**, such as reduced rates for movement between flats and workplaces, could increase adoption. Combining public-private partnerships and linking the service to broader initiatives like the Sustainable Tourism Pact were suggested to ensure long-term sustainability.

Ensuring that the service is **accessible** to all users – including newly arrived residents, families with children, and people with disabilities – was highlighted as a key factor for success. Participants also noted the importance of social integration and including civil society in implementation to strengthen **community engagement**.

To raise **awareness and encourage adoption**, participants suggested using visual and social strategies, such as making cargo bikes highly visible or adding QR codes to provide information. Best practice platforms, such as TouristMut, were cited as useful models for public registration and promotion of exemplary events.

Finally, **operational readiness** was considered critical for scaling. Adaptation in rural areas or smaller villages may require **additional facilities, fair pricing, and tailored logistics support**. Lessons from Thessaloniki (Greece) and Graz (Austria) emphasised the need to coordinate with local authorities to avoid legal restrictions and ensure city structures remain open to cargo bike operations.

Figure 9 Screenshots of the Miro board used by participants during the first ELC session

3. Session 2

3.1. Overview

The second session of the ELC took place on 25 September 2025 from 11:00 to 12:00 CET on Zoom and was organised by SIC (Sweden), with support from project partners.

Figure 10 Social media banner promoting the second ELC session

The seminar was focused on testing a mobile micro-hub with cargo bikes piloted by a local courier service, with insights from the case of Leipzig, Germany.

Figure 11 Challenges and key takeaways from the Leipzig pilot

The session was opened with a welcome from the moderator, followed by an introduction by Michael Thele, Innovation Researcher at Salzburg Research and SuCoLo Project Coordinator.

This was followed by a pilot presentation by **Viola Süß**, Research Associate at the Logistics Living Lab, Leipzig University, and a Q&A session with the speaker.

Participants then engaged in breakout room discussions to collaborate and share insights.

The event concluded with closing remarks summarising the key points of the session.

Figure 12 Agenda of the second ELC session

The event was moderated by Harris Stamatopoulos (SIC), while representatives of the project partners facilitated the activities in the breakout rooms. Both the moderator and the facilitators received instructions and guidelines specifically prepared for the second ELC session.

In the second session, three groups were formed among interested participants, with discussions held in two rounds, each consisting of 4-6 participants per group. The discussions were supported using Miro.

Figure 13 Second ELC session, 25 September 2025 (Zoom)

3.2. Synthesis and outcome

During the first discussion round, participants reflected on the Leipzig pilot by assessing its most relevant features and sharing observations on its effectiveness, innovation, and potential areas for further development.

Participants emphasised that the pilot stands out as a real-life, operational solution, with actual deliveries already being carried out rather than remaining at a conceptual or experimental stage. This practical implementation was seen as a key strength, demonstrating that the solution is already functioning under real market conditions.

The mobile **micro-hub approach** was highlighted as a flexible and cost-efficient solution, particularly well-suited to smaller logistics providers that may not have the capacity to establish permanent hub infrastructure. Participants noted that the mobility of the hubs helps overcome spatial constraints in dense urban environments and allows logistics operations to adapt to varying demand patterns. Some suggested that expanding the model into a connected system of hubs across a wider urban area could further enhance coverage and operational efficiency.

Cargo-bike delivery was identified as a core strength of the pilot, especially in inner-city zones where access for conventional vehicles is restricted.

Participants pointed out that **local good conditions in Leipzig**, such as favourable topography and supportive traffic regulations, make this solution especially effective. However, they also stressed that these local factors are not universally applicable, and that replication in other cities would require adjustments to local infrastructure, policies, and urban layouts.

Discussions also addressed broader logistics challenges within the pilot. Participants described **last-mile delivery** as a highly competitive sector with structural inefficiencies, noting issues such as dispersed pick-up points, scheduling constraints, and coordination across supply chains. The potential extension of the pilot to peripheral districts and nearby municipalities, including Halle and Lützschena-Stahmeln (Leipzig), was viewed positively and seen as an important step in testing the model's scalability and adaptability.

From a **social perspective**, the pilot was recognised for promoting fair labour practices, as couriers are employed under standard contracts rather than gig-based arrangements. Participants considered this an important contribution to social sustainability.

At the same time, the operational model, which combines cargo bikes with limited use of motor vehicles to support cycling logistics, was regarded as a balanced solution that aligns **environmental goals** with practical delivery needs.

Several **external barriers** were also discussed. Participants identified political decision-making and regulatory frameworks as key factors influencing the pilot's future expansion. In addition, cooperation with large logistics operators was described as challenging, particularly due to limited data-sharing practices and reliance on proprietary digital systems. While technological solutions were generally considered adequate, market conditions (such as pricing pressures and competition with established providers) were seen as more significant obstacles.

In the second round of discussion, participants focused on the possibilities and limitations of adapting and scaling the Leipzig pilot to other cities and regions, with particular attention to differences between urban, peripheral, and rural contexts.

Participants noted that replicating the pilot in **rural areas** presents specific challenges, as there are fewer suitable locations for micro-hubs and lower delivery densities. Nevertheless, they emphasised the importance of exploring ways to better connect rural and peripheral areas through more sustainable logistics solutions, potentially by strengthening links between urban hubs and surrounding regions.

A key issue raised was user **behaviour and acceptance**. Participants pointed out that scaling the model would require changes in consumer habits, as many people still prefer travelling to city centres for shopping rather than using online services. Encouraging adoption of alternative delivery models was therefore seen as an important but challenging aspect of implementation in new regions.

Several participants reflected on the transferability of the pilot to **southern European contexts**, using Rethymno (Greece) as an example. They noted that the city's historic centre and restricted car access could make cargo-bike logistics particularly suitable. In addition, existing sustainable logistics strategies in Rethymno were seen as a supportive framework for testing similar solutions. At the same time, participants highlighted **technical constraints, limited space, and accessibility issues** as potential barriers that would need to be addressed in close cooperation with local authorities.

Moreover, participants stressed that strong **institutional partnerships and municipal support** are essential for securing access to space, aligning with traffic regulations, and ensuring long-term viability. It was mentioned that Leipzig is a positive example, where active support from the city and collaboration with FULMO helped address challenges related to micro-hub location and flexibility.

Participants also highlighted operational lessons learned from Leipzig, including the value of **flexible micro-hub placement that can change daily**, depending on business needs. The economic stability of FULMO and its openness to expanding services to peripheral areas (such as deliveries of fresh produce and coffee) were seen as important factors contributing to the pilot's resilience and scalability.

Engagement with **local community** was identified as another key success factor. Participants noted that strong local knowledge, good communication with citizens, and active participation in surveys contributed to high-quality insights and improved acceptance of the pilot in Leipzig.

Finally, participants compared challenges across different contexts. In Greece, the lack of enforcement of traffic regulations was highlighted as a major obstacle, as vans are often able to access areas that would otherwise favour cargo-bike solutions. Similar concerns were raised in relation to Merano, where insufficient political pressure and underdeveloped infrastructure were seen as limiting factors for scaling sustainable logistics initiatives.

4. Session 3

4.1. Overview

The final, third, ELC session took place on 2 October 2025 from 11:00 to 12:00 CET on Zoom and explored how digital nudges on e-commerce platforms can encourage the use of cargo bike delivery, drawing on insights from Salzburg, Austria.

Figure 15 Social media banner promoting the third ELC session

The speakers at the event were **Michael Thelen**, Innovation Researcher at Salzburg Research, and **Alexander Planitzer**, CEO and Co-Founder of VIABIRDS Technologies.

<h4>Challenges</h4> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Balancing sustainability with convenience & cost - While surveys show willingness to wait or pay more, many respondents in workshops often prioritized speed and low cost Scalability & generalizability - Nudges tested among Austrian shoppers may not translate easily to other regions, consumer cultures, or market conditions (e.g., the worth of a 3-euro gift card in Austria vs. Switzerland) Ecological validity - A simulator may not fully replicate the pressures, incentives, or habits people face in <i>real</i> online shopping, so behavior might differ Longitudinal effects - The study captures short-term choices, but may not reflect how nudges work over repeated interactions in real life 		<h4>Key takeaways</h4> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cargo bikes are a viable solution for sustainable last-mile delivery Consumers play a crucial role in sustainable delivery choices but often face a "green gap" between their intentions and actual behavior Digital nudging, which is widely used, can help bridge this gap Our study tested six types of nudges in a webshop prototype with Austrian online shoppers to evaluate effectiveness Preliminary results suggest both potential benefits and risks (including backfiring effects), highlighting the need for practical, user-friendly nudges 	
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Figure 16 Challenges and key takeaways from the Salzburg pilot

As with the previous sessions, the event was organised by SIC (Sweden), with support from all project partners.

The agenda followed a similar format to earlier events. The session opened with a welcome from the moderator, followed by a brief introduction to the project. This was followed by a pilot presentation delivered by Michael Thelen and Alexander Planitzer. After the presentations, a Q&A session gave participants the opportunity to ask questions and engage in discussion.

EUROPEAN LEARNING CIRCLE

SuCoLo Seminar 3: *Harnessing digital nudges on e-commerce sites to promote cargo bike delivery - in the case of Salzburg, Austria*

AGENDA

- **PILOT PRESENTATION**
Speakers:
 - **Michael Thelen**, Innovation Researcher, Salzburg Research
 - **Alexander Planitzer**, CEO & Co-Founder, VIABIRDS Technologies
- **Q&A WITH THE SPEAKERS**
- **WORK IN THE BREAKOUT ROOMS**
- **DISCUSSION IN THE MAIN ROOM**
- **CLOSING REMARKS**

Date: 2 October, 2025 | Time: 11:00 - 12:00 CET

Figure 17 Agenda of the first ELC session

The event was moderated by **Svitlana Baliuk** (SIC) and the project partners representatives facilitated the work in the breakout rooms. Both the moderator and the facilitators received instructions and guidelines specifically prepared for the first ELC session.

In the third session, five groups were formed, and discussions were conducted in two rounds, each with 6-8 participants per group, using Miro as a support tool.

Figure 18 Third ELC session, 02 October 2025 (Zoom)

4.2. Synthesis and outcome

During the first round of group discussions, participants analysed the Salzburg pilot and shared their views on it. Participants agreed that the pilot demonstrates strong potential, especially when viewed as part of a **broader logistics chain**.

Integrating **digital nudging** into existing delivery systems was seen to optimise resource use, particularly through the deployment of micro-hubs and the more efficient allocation of delivery vehicles. The use of digital nudges was widely regarded as one of the most innovative aspects of the pilot. Participants highlighted that nudges can influence not only the choice of delivery mode but also the selection of logistics providers, which is often closely linked to trust in the service.

The option for consumers to choose between van delivery and cargo bike – without additional cost – was considered particularly relevant, although participants noted that cost structures and efficiency vary significantly depending on local conditions. Providing customers with multiple **delivery options**, supported by clear and accessible information, was considered essential. Importantly, participants emphasised that nudges should **not focus solely on environmental benefits but also include other motivating factors**, such as social norms, reliability, and working conditions. The discussion also broadened to include the **social dimension of sustainability**. Participants stressed that delivery choices should not only reflect environmental considerations but also account for the working conditions of couriers.

Examples from other contexts, such as the BündelHeinz project in Vienna, were discussed as promising approaches, particularly where nudging is combined with delivery consolidation and visually engaging cues.

Discussions also focused on the importance of **tailoring nudges** to specific target groups. Participants noted that age, lifestyle, socio-demographic background, and socio-psychological factors all influence decision-making. Presenting information in a **simple, visually appealing way and adapting messaging** for different audiences, potentially through targeted **social campaigns**, was seen as key to increasing impact. **Regional identity** and **locally relevant examples** were also highlighted as effective tools for strengthening engagement and trust.

At the same time, participants acknowledged that **convincing new or less sustainability-aware users remains challenging**, as individuals already interested in sustainability are more likely to respond positively to nudges.

Alternative models, such as runner-based or walking deliveries observed in Stockholm, were mentioned as innovative but also raised questions about long-term physical strain and fairness. Making the **human impact of delivery choices more visible**, through checklists or benefit summaries, was suggested to support more informed consumer decisions.

Additionally, participants noted that many **customers don't want to pay extra for sustainable delivery options**, and that online shoppers often default to conventional delivery providers.

The discussion highlighted differing dynamics between B2B and B2C contexts, as well as the difficulty of positioning sustainable options within competitive market environments.

In the second round of discussions, participants explored how digital nudges could be made effective and practical for broader use across online shops and platforms, as well as which additional nudging approaches could online shops use.

Participants agreed that the **design and selection of nudges** is complex and context-dependent. While cargo-bike logistics is already a well-established solution in some cities, its effectiveness depends on local infrastructure, fleet capacity, and cooperation with retail partners. Participants highlighted that nudges should be aligned with business realities and integrated into existing retail and logistics workflows, rather than introduced as isolated features.

Participants from different groups mentioned the importance of **offering customers meaningful choices**, supported by clear incentives. Simply presenting a sustainable delivery option was seen as insufficient. Participants stressed that nudges must actively guide decisions. Setting cargo-bike delivery as the **default option**, where feasible, was highlighted as a particularly powerful approach. At the same time, flexibility was considered important, as different product categories (such as refrigerated or fresh goods) require tailored solutions.

Participants discussed the relevance of different **nudging strategies for B2C and B2B** contexts. In B2B logistics, nudges linked to operational efficiency, reliability, and cost predictability were seen as more effective, while consumer-facing platforms benefit more from emotional, visual, and value-based cues. Experiences from other projects indicated that emotional nudges often outperform purely price-based incentives.

Several types of nudges were identified as especially promising:

- **instant feedback mechanisms**, such as showing immediate savings or reduced emissions at checkout;
- **visual and emotional elements**, including icons, mascots, badges, or progress bars;
- **loyalty-based incentives**, such as points, rewards, or customer recognition for repeated sustainable choices;
- **social nudges**, including recommendations, sharing options, or highlighting community norms;
- **transparency tools**, such as carbon footprint checklists or emissions comparisons.

Participants emphasised that **customer experience is often more influential than price alone**. While many customers tend to choose the cheapest or fastest delivery option, participants noted that users may accept longer delivery times or alternative options if these are clearly explained and framed as beneficial. Providing transparent, easy-to-understand information, covering environmental, social, and economic impacts, was considered essential.

Website usability and accessibility were also highlighted as critical success factors. Participants noted that a **simple, well-structured interface**, barrier-free design, and smooth technical performance are necessary to prevent frustration and drop-offs during checkout. **Technical issues**, such as slow response times or system glitches, were identified as potential barriers that can undermine even well-designed nudges.

The discussion also addressed the **role of trust and social connection**. Participants suggested that knowing who delivers the package, or feeling a personal connection to the

service, can positively influence behaviour. Partnerships with local shops, discount schemes across networks, and community-based approaches were seen as effective ways to strengthen trust and acceptance.

5. Conclusion and next steps

Across the three ELC sessions held in September-October 2025, participants analysed the SoCoLo pilots in Merano, Leipzig and Salzburg and discussed opportunities for their improvement and scaling. According to the results, all three pilots demonstrate clear potential to contribute to more sustainable and inclusive urban logistics.

The first ELC session, which focused on the Merano pilot, highlighted its strong potential to support sustainable and inclusive urban logistics, particularly when integrated with city initiatives and stakeholder networks. Participants emphasised the importance of adapting the model to local infrastructure conditions, strengthening cooperation with local businesses, and ensuring inclusive design to enable transferability to other small and medium-sized cities.

The second session confirmed the Leipzig pilot as a mature, real-life logistics solution with high scalability potential, supported by flexible micro-hubs and cargo-bike delivery. Its operational readiness, combined with strong municipal support and adaptable hub placement, was seen as a key enabler for replication in other urban contexts. Participants noted that successful scaling would depend on regulatory alignment, access to suitable space for hubs, and the ability to extend services to peripheral and rural areas.

The final session, which focused on the Salzburg pilot, underscored the value of digital nudging as an innovative tool to influence delivery choices and promote sustainable logistics. Participants concluded that nudges are most effective when combined with clear information, social sustainability considerations, and tailored communication strategies that address diverse user groups and competitive market conditions. The transferability of digital nudging approaches was considered high, provided that nudges are adapted to local cultural contexts, integrated into existing digital platforms, and aligned with market realities in both B2B and B2C environments.

Overall, the ELC sessions confirm that sustainable last-mile logistics solutions are technically feasible and socially desirable, however, their success depends on effective communication, supportive governance, inclusive design and context-sensitive scaling strategies.

The following cities can make use of the outcomes from the ELC discussions, particularly the second round of each session, which focused on scaling and adapting the pilots to other urban contexts. They received a clear framework and practical ideas that could be applied locally. However, city representatives noted that full implementation may be limited by local infrastructure and expertise. While not all aspects of the pilots can be directly transferred, certain elements can be adopted. In particular, the shared use of cargo bikes drew strong interest, with demand appearing to grow steadily.

As a next step, the project will focus on translating the lessons learned from the ELC sessions into concrete implementation actions. This includes refining pilot designs, strengthening stakeholder engagement at local level and further testing scalable and inclusive logistics solutions in follower cities.

Moreover, the inputs from the sessions were taken into account in the planning and preparation of workshops for the following cities, organised under Task 4.3 Adaptation Plans of Follower Cities. The feedback and insights from the sessions were analysed to shape the structure and

content of the workshops. One-page summaries for each pilot city, based on presentations during the ELC, were prepared and shared with registered participants prior to the workshops to guide discussions and ensure relevant topics were addressed. Additionally, all the cities that participated in the ELC were invited to the workshops. The results of the ELC will also be shared with European city platforms, such as CIVITAS, ELTIS, POLIS, and others. The insights will also be considered when preparing and organising take-up measures in follower cities, for example during the development of Deliverable D5.4 Recommendations for Sustainable Urban Bicycle Logistics Policies.